

HARMFUL ALGAE NEWS

An IOC Newsletter on toxic algae and algal blooms

No. 6

This issue is devoted to domoic acid in North America

Guest editor's notes

As one steeped in the conventional wisdom that only phytoflagellates (excepting cyanobacteria) were phycotoxin producers, it came as a surprise to me that the capacity to synthesize potent mammalian toxins is shared with diatoms. Under-flagellated - thus comparatively boring to watch under the microscope (Victorian diatom gardens notwithstanding), and of limited apparent use other than in such utilitarian products as polishing compounds, diatoms always seemed to lack a certain 'je ne sais quoi' compared to flagellates. Yes, as first among equals at the base of marine food chains, diatoms are certainly important, but roughage for copepods is hardly a sexy role. Frankly, I'm a bit disappointed to admit diatoms into the first ranks of marine 'killer' organisms! Perhaps *Pseudonitzschia* really produce pseudo-domoic acid.

On a more serious note, the recent National Shellfisheries Association Annual Meeting in Portland, Oregon, USA (31 May-3 June, 1993) hosted a special mini-symposium, sponsored by SEAGRANT, on 'Harmful Phytoplankton and Shellfish Interactions'. It was noteworthy that the risk of ASP is of particular concern to the Pacific shellfisheries industry and regulatory agencies, as reflected in the fact that more than half of the invited oral presentations were focused on domoic acid (DA) distribution and effects. Local reports from the Pacific northwest have indicated that > 250,000 people may be involved in the recreational razor clam fishery - obviously a nightmare to monitor adequately! Re-

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Toxicity and *Pseudonitzschia pungens* in Prince Edward Island, 1987-1992.

In late 1987 an unusual series of human illnesses and deaths was determined to be caused by consumption of mussels contaminated by domoic acid (DA)⁽¹⁾. This potent neurotoxin, produced by the pennate diatom *Pseudonitzschia* (formerly *Nitzschia*) *pungens* f. *multiseries*⁽²⁾, was found during late autumnal blooms in estuaries of eastern Prince Edward Island (PEI), in Atlantic Canada. The chronology of these events⁽³⁾ and many other aspects of these phenomena have been reviewed recently⁽⁴⁾.

Prior to 1987, it was believed that PEI and nearby regions of the Gulf of St. Lawrence were free from harmful algal problems and no regular monitoring program for phycotoxin-producing phytoplankton was in place. Following the tragic events of 1987, projects were undertaken to determine the spatial and temporal patterns of abundance of *P. pungens* and occurrences of DA toxicity in phytoplankton and shellfish. A further aim was to acquire a predictive capability by relating the physical, chemical, biological and hydrographic parameters governing the timing and intensity of these blooms.

Large scale meteorological events appear to be important in determining the magnitude of *P. pungens* blooms. The 1987 bloom was likely to have been immense, although we can only speculate. The summer of 1987 was the driest in many years, resulting in a drop in the water table and low river runoff. Rain in September (while significant) served only to raise water tables, not to increase runoff. Heavy rains followed in November, leading to a sudden increase in runoff, which presumably delivered a large input of nutrients to the Cardigan River estuary within a short period, hence provoking a bloom of *P. pungens*. The heavy rainfall was followed by an extended period of calm weather characterized by light southerly winds,

Pseudonitzschia pungens f. *multiseries* (x6000) from Danish waters. Photo: Ø. Moestrup.

which may have been important to the retention of the phytoplankton bloom in the estuary. It is not known where the seed population for the bloom originated, however back calculations were used to estimate the *P. pungens* bloom maximum at 3 to 4 x 10⁶ cells/L.

The meteorological events of 1988 were similar to those of 1987, but were less severe. The summer was dry, yet not as dry as in 1987, and the water tables were not as low. In 1988, the autumn rainfall started earlier and the mid-November weather was not as calm. A very strong southeasterly gale in early November injected large amounts of nutrients into the water column, probably including major fluxes from benthic sources. The toxic *P. pungens* bloom in 1988 reached 1.2 x 10⁶ cells/L. The morphologically similar (but non-toxic) f. *pungens* formed two blooms which peaked earlier than the toxicogenic f. *multiseries* bloom.

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searchers at Battelle Marine Sciences Laboratory divided toxic razor clams from Washington State into edible and non-edible fractions, then determined DA levels in each tissue compartment. For edible tissues the hierarchy was as follows: foot > adductor > siphon > mantle, whereas for non-edible components the toxin content in decreasing order of importance was gonads > siphon tip > digestive gland/gill. This is markedly different from the distribution expected for PSP toxins. Also, surprisingly, measurable DA was retained in tissues for more than four months, and archived samples indicated that DA was present even after eight years in storage. Short-term feeding experiments using *P. pungens* f. *multiseriis* from Galveston Bay to toxify oysters, *Crassostrea virginica*, conducted at Texas A&M University, indicated that most DA was concentrated in digestive tissues, with virtually no detoxification occurring in < 72 hours after cessation of feeding.

A review of DA in western Washington State waters, from the University of Washington, noted that at least three known DA-producing *Pseudonitzschia* species (*pungens* f. *multiseriis*, *pseudodelicatissima*, and *australis*) are present in this area. However, *Pseudonitzschia* was apparently absent from the surf zone during the most prominent DA incident. A detailed survey by Texas A&M researchers and their collaborators on the Pacific coast has attempted to determine the taxonomic affinities and geographical range of suspected DA-producing diatoms from southern California northward to the Columbia River. A number of clonal isolates are being screened for their capacity to produce DA in culture. Good luck to all concerned.

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British Columbia: Implications of the North American west coast experience

Until 1991, the only region known for domoic acid (DA) produced by diatoms was the Atlantic coast of Canada, particularly the east coast of Prince Edward Island. This was peculiar because the diatoms implicated in that region are not confined to those waters, being common in many temperate coastal regions in both the northern and southern hemispheres. For example, *Pseudonitzschia pungens* is particularly common off the west coast of Vancouver Island, British Columbia, with highest numbers found in July and August, although not in great abundance (max. 10^6 cells/L). Both *P. pungens* forms are present in Sechart Inlet, a classic mainland fjordal inlet on Vancouver Island, where they occur primarily in late summer, with f. *pungens* predominating. Another species known to produce DA, *P. pseudodelicatissima*, is also present in British Columbia, although its distribution, abundance, and toxicity is not well known since it is difficult to distinguish under routine analytical conditions.

The deaths of seabirds in Monterey Bay, California in September 1991, following the consumption of anchovies, was traced to another related diatom, *P. australis* (see article by Garrison and Walz, p. 5). Thus, the presence of DA on the west coast was demonstrated in dramatic fashion, yet the incident seemed very unusual. Seabird mortalities suspected to be due to phycotoxins have occasionally happened on the west coast of North America and in other parts of the world, but these were attributed to PSP. In fact, the knowledge that anchovies can accumulate enough DA in their guts to harm birds is quite alarming since anchovies are in many foodchains, including our own. This event caused quite a stir at the Fifth International Conference on Toxic Marine Phytoplankton, Rhode Island (Oct.–Nov. 1991), which followed soon after; it was another example of a newly implicated species doing a new diabolical thing with a recently discovered toxin. (This was eclipsed in dramatic impact by Joanne Burkholder's fish-killing dinoflagellate from North Carolina – which even made *Time Magazine* and *National Geographic*).

The illness of some Washington

State residents drew attention to the presence of DA in razor clams (confirmed by the Institute for Marine Biosciences, NRC, Halifax) from open coast localities in Washington and northern Oregon. The fact that west coast mussels were effectively free of DA was puzzling at first, but this was interpreted subsequently to be due to rapid detoxification by mussels and remarkably prolonged retention by razor clams. The causative bloom had vanished by the time the toxicity was noted and the clam guts were free of *Pseudonitzschia*, a fact consistent with the above interpretation. However, this also opened the possibility that another source might have been the cause. Shortly thereafter DA was detected at low levels in southern Alaska. Was it conceivable that a bloom of the same species could have extended along practically the entire west coast (not necessarily coincidentally)? The puzzling absence of DA-positive analyses from the coast of British Columbia is at least partially attributable to the fact that razor clams were not part of the phycotoxin sampling program at the time. Nevertheless, the presence of DA was confirmed subsequently on the west coast of Vancouver Island in 1992.

Another new dimension was added in December 1991 when it was discovered that Dungeness crabs from Washington and Oregon, including some shipped unknowingly to Japan, had DA in their viscera. This was the first definite implication of a phycotoxin in these widely eaten crabs (PSP has been subsequently detected in west coast crab viscera, but that is another story). Its presence was restricted to the viscera, but unfortunately the crabs are often cooked whole, at which time the DA enters the meat. Also causing concern is the fact that the viscera are sometimes eaten separately as 'crab butter'. The concern of Canadian regulatory authorities regarding the occurrences of DA along the Pacific coast of the USA has led to an expanded shellfish monitoring program for DA in shellfish species, including crabs, at selected sites in British Columbia. It is not known how the crabs acquire the toxin: are they able to ingest a planktonic bloom that has

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Neurotoxicity by domoic acid and okadaic acid

In 1987, cultured Canadian mussels produced an intoxication characterized by neurological problems, such as headache, confusion, and loss of memory, particularly severe at times⁽⁹⁾. The syndrome was named amnesic shellfish poisoning (ASP). Neuronal damage was found in the hippocampus and amygdala of four patients who did die later on⁽¹¹⁾. The toxin responsible for such intoxication was identified as a rare tricarboxylic amino acid, named domoic acid (DA), possibly produced by the unicellular alga *Pseudonitzschia pungens*, and accumulated by the cultured mussels⁽¹²⁾. Since 1987, DA has been found in a variety of seafood in the USA and Canada. In November 1991, on the west coast of the USA, a large number of cormorants died as a consequence of ingesting anchovies contaminated with DA. DA has been classified as an excitatory amino acid (EAA) which action occurs through the ionotropic NON-NMDA (N-methyl aspartic acid) subtype of EAA receptors^(6,7,8). In mammalian central nervous systems, EAA

receptors (of the NMDA and NON-NMDA type) are activated mainly by the dicarboxylic amino acids, aspartic acid and glutamic acid, which seem to be the major excitatory neurotransmitters, and appear to be also responsible for neuronal death following ischemic accidents such as strokes^(1,5). We have reported on the biochemical and toxicological effects of a DA-containing toxic mussel extract, using primary cultures of cerebellar neurons^(6,7,8).

Using this experimental system we have also investigated the neurotoxic properties of okadaic acid (OKA), another toxin of algal origin which may be present in seafood, and known to produce diarrhetic shellfish poisoning (DSP). The biochemical properties of OKA have been recently reviewed^(2,4). Thus, this toxin has been found to be a potent tumor promotor. In intact cells, OKA produces a great increase in phosphorylation of several proteins, and modulates a variety of cellular functions such as smooth muscle contraction, fatty acid biosynthesis, protein synthesis, and

catecholamine synthesis and secretion. Calcium influx through voltage-sensitive calcium channels (VSCC) may be increased by OKA treatment, although opposite effects of OKA have been reported on calcium-dependent phenomena such as neurotransmitter release. OKA does not appear to alter only VSCC. Recent data indicated that OKA may increase the ionic influx through the ionotropic NON-NMDA type of EAA receptors. EAA receptors and VSCC may be responsible for neuronal degeneration^(1,3,4). We have recently described the neurotoxic effects of OKA considering the possible involvement of VSCC and EAA receptor in the neurotoxic effects of OKA in neuronal cultures^(3,4).

Domoic Acid

Cultured cerebellar neurons were exposed to several dilutions of either mussel extract from amnesic shellfish poison-containing mussels (AEX), or purified DA, the alleged amnesic poison in the mussels. Surprisingly, when the neurotoxicity curve produced by AEX was compared to the concentration-dependent neurotoxicity curve produced by DA, 50% reduction in neuronal survival was achieved at a dilution of AEX containing 1- μ M DA as compared with 8- μ M for purified DA alone, indicating that subtoxic concentrations of DA may become neurotoxic when in AEX. In order to verify that DA was the only substance responsible for the neurotoxicity of AEX, several concentrations of purified DA were added to a non-toxic mussel extract, used as a control (CEX). We found that the addition of non-toxic concentrations of DA to CEX, produced neurotoxicity similar to AEX. By using specific antagonists for NMDA and NON-NMDA receptors, and chromatographic techniques, we have found that such potentiation of DA neurotoxicity in mussel extract is due to mussels' high content of aspartic and glutamic acid. Thus, DA, by acting at the NON-NMDA receptor, is able to enhance the action of aspartic and glutamic acid at the NMDA receptor, beyond physiological control. The result is an excessive excitation which may lead to neuronal death. In mussels, the combined concentration of glutamic and aspartic acid reported in the literature⁽⁷⁾

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'sunk out', or are they getting DA from a benthic source either directly or indirectly?

As yet unpublished results of a field study we conducted in Barkley Sound on the west coast of Vancouver Island in the summer of 1992 (first of a two-year study) revealed that both *P. pungens* and *P. australis* bloomed within the bay, but in sequence. The former species was not associated with DA in shellfish, yet there was a rise in DA levels (according to the Department of Fisheries and Oceans, Inspection Branch) immediately following the collapse of the latter bloom. These data suggest that, in general, *P. australis* is the primary source of DA on the west coast. This, of course, requires confirmation by testing *P. australis* cultures from the northwest coast for DA production, and the determination of what role, if any, *P. pungens* plays in DA toxicity on the Pacific coast.

Since *P. australis* has not been recorded previously from the west coast, or even from the northern hemisphere, there is a natural tendency to wonder if it represents a recent introduction via

ship's ballast water or other means. Several points can be noted in this regard. First, this species greatly resembles *P. seriata* (in fact, its synonym is *Nitzschia pseudoseriata*), differing primarily in having a more symmetrical valve shape. Therefore, it could easily have been misidentified (as *N. seriata*) in earlier west coast collections. This species was not even included in Esther Cupp's much-used taxonomic reference on west coast diatoms, but only its look-alike, *P. seriata*. Second, its known distribution is practically the same as *P. pungens* f. *multiseriata* (Argentina, British Columbia), although the latter also has east coast records. The matter should be resolvable by looking at archived samples from which *P. seriata* was previously recorded (as *N. seriata*). Records of the *N. seriata* from California are particularly suspect since Grethe Hasle believes that this is a very cold northern species (Cupp found it in Alaska).

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averages at 0.74 mmol/100 g fresh weight, although it may vary from 0.3 to 1.62 mmol/100 g fresh weight. Nevertheless, human cases of intoxication attributable to mussels' high EAA content have never been reported. These considerations reinforce the idea that DA may have been necessary for the occurrence of neurological problems. Moreover, our data suggest that concentrations of DA that per se would not have been sufficient to cause neurotoxicity, could have induced neurotoxicity in the presence of adequate concentrations of NMDA receptor agonists. The relevance of our results in the explanation of the neurological problems reported during the Canadian episode of intoxication will need further investigation using different experimental systems. Recent data from behavioural studies in rodents did show that low doses of DA in extracts of contaminated mussels were significantly more potent than the same doses of purified DA⁽¹⁰⁾. Thus, this observation may be explained by our finding of a synergistic interaction between EAAs, assuming a significant passage of alimentary-related EAAs through the blood brain barrier.

Okadaic Acid

Okadaic acid (OKA), at concentrations as low as 0.5 - 1 nM may produce neurotoxicity⁽³⁾. OKA action is characterized by a slow disintegration of neurites, followed by visible swelling of cell bodies, and later by cellular death. Neurotoxicity by OKA was not characterized by any fast darkening/swelling of the neurons (characteristic of EAAs), which remained unaltered for up to 16 hours, when degeneration of the neuronal network started to become evident^(3,4). After 24 hours exposure, OKA led to a complete degeneration of the neuronal network, while around 70% of the neuronal cell bodies were still able to stain for the vital probe fluorescein diacetate, and therefore they were considered alive by this criterion⁽³⁾. After 48 hours exposure to OKA most of the neuronal bodies had degenerated. The concentration producing 50% neurotoxicity shifted from around 7.5 nM at 24 h, to around 1.8 nM at 48 h. The majority of cerebellar neurons in culture are glutamatergic granule cells, which may release EAAs, such as glutamic acid and aspartic acid, upon depolarization-induced calcium entry via VSCC. Such endogenous EAA release may produce neurotoxicity⁽³⁾. Thus, we

have explored the possibility that neurotoxicity by OKA may involve endogenous EAA release. Blockers of VSCC, as well as EAA receptor antagonists, completely prevented neurotoxicity by endogenous EAA release, but failed to protect from OKA neurotoxicity. The reported increase in ionic permeability of the NON-NMDA channel subsequent to exposure to OKA may not be relevant for the neurotoxic effect of OKA. In fact, OKA failed to potentiate DA toxicity⁽⁴⁾.

It is well documented that OKA is a potent inhibitor of protein phosphatases PP1 and PP2A, and therefore leads to a great increase in protein phosphorylation when added to intact cells⁽²⁾. The inhibition of PP1 and PP2A activity *in vitro* occurs at concentrations of OKA comparable to those we found to be neurotoxic^(2,3). Some of the proteins affected could be particularly important for the neuronal functioning, as recently discussed⁽³⁾. OKA is capable of altering the activity of Ca²⁺/calmodulin-dependent protein kinase II (CaM-K), which participate in the storage of synaptic weight. Thus, OKA-mediated disruption of the neuronal network might be reflecting changes in the phosphorylating equilibrium determined by CaM-K activity. Other phosphorylated proteins may also be considered to play a role in OKA neurotoxicity, such as synapsin I, which controls vesicular neurotransmitter release. On the other hand, the microtubule-associated protein 2 (MAP2), which is increasingly phosphorylated in the presence of OKA, has been suggested to be necessary for neuronal cells to undergo normal morphological differentiation including neurite extension and cessation of cell division. Another microtubule-associated protein, tau, appears to be abnormally phosphorylated in some neurodegenerative disorders such as Alzheimer's disease, and the appearance of hyperphosphorylated tau and neurodegeneration following microinjections of OKA in rodent brain has been observed. Moreover, OKA has recently been shown to modulate the processing of Alzheimer B/A4 amyloid precursor protein.

Conclusions

The neurotoxic properties of DA and OKA deserve further studies in order to fully evaluate the risk represented by ASP and DSP for human health. Caution must be exercised when consider-

ing the toxicological properties of each toxin, since they may produce unexpected synergisms. For ASP, the contemporary presence in the brain of concentrations of DA insufficient alone to be toxic, together with excitatory amino acids of diet-related origin, may have been relevant in the occurrence of the neurological problems reported. On the other hand, the slow neurotoxic effect of OKA may be important when considering its lipophilicity and its possible accumulation in lipophilic structures such as the brain.

This investigation has also allowed the preparation of a new bioassay based on the utilization of cultures of cerebellar neurons for the determination of the presence of ASP and DSP in shellfish (as well as in other types of seafood). It should be noted that this assay, based on live cells, allows us to determine the presence of toxicity not only by DA or OKA, but by any DA-like or OKA-like toxin. In this respect it may be an interesting alternative to the mouse assay, in which respect it may offer higher sensitivity.

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North Pacific coast of USA: Toxic diatom blooms and domoic acid

Domoic acid (DA)-producing blooms of *Pseudonitzschia australis* were first recognized on the Pacific coast of the United States at Monterey Bay, California in the late summer of 1991. This toxic event was signalled by the death of several brown pelicans and Brandt's cormorants in mid-September of 1991. DA was found in bird tissues and linked to feeding on northern anchovy, and ultimately to *P. australis* cells upon which the anchovy had been feeding⁽¹⁾. At the time of these seabird deaths, no DA measurements were being made, but plankton samples indicated that *P. australis* abundances were approximately 6.5 to 20×10^4 cells/L⁽²⁾. Measurements of DA levels at the University of California at Santa Cruz (UCSC) showed that toxin was present throughout November. Plankton analysis showed a peak of *P. australis* abundance in late November, with cell counts reaching $> 1 \times 10^6$ /L (Fig. 1a). Cells from the November bloom were isolated and shown to produce DA in culture⁽³⁾. No seabird deaths were associ-

ated with this November peak, probably because the anchovy were no longer congregated near the shore.

However, there was also an occurrence of DA poisoning to the north in Washington State during November, when fishermen had consumed DA-contaminated razor clams⁽⁴⁾. In addition to the razor clams, DA was also detected in the viscera of Dungeness crabs from the north Pacific coast⁽⁵⁾. Although no plankton samples were collected in Oregon and Washington during this event, it seems likely that the events in California and those further north were linked.

A toxic bloom of *P. australis* reappeared in 1992 during our monitoring program. In net-collected plankton samples, DA was detected from 10 to 20 November 1992. *P. australis* densities reached a maximum of approximately 4×10^5 cells/L during this bloom⁽⁶⁾. Although DA was measured in top smelt collected during the November bloom, and cormorants were observed diving and feeding on these fish, no seabird

deaths were reported during this period. Interestingly, and unlike the 1991 event, DA was not detected in California mussels, which are sampled by the California Department of Health Services as part of a PSP and DA monitoring program⁽⁷⁾. Therefore, questions remain about whether this species is an appropriate 'sentinel' organism to detect DA toxicity on the Pacific coast.

In our preliminary examination of archived plankton samples at UCSC, we confirmed that there were massive blooms of *P. australis* in the winter of 1977, but the species had been misidentified as *P. seriata*⁽³⁾. Thus, although blooms of *P. australis* have previously been present, there is no evidence of toxicity in Monterey Bay prior to 1991. During our monitoring of the plankton in February 1992, we also

New publication

The Proceedings of the Third Canadian Workshop on Harmful Marine Algae, held at the Maurice Lamontagne Institute, Mont-Joli (May 12-14, 1992), are now available as a published Technical Report. Many issues related to domoic acid problems in a Canadian context were addressed at this Workshop. Address reprint requests to:

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found *P. pungens* f. *multiseries*⁽⁸⁾, but no toxin was detected in net-concentrated plankton samples during this period.

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Fig. 1a,b: *Pseudonitzschia australis* abundances during the autumns of 1991 and 1992.

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Pseudonitzschia/Nitzschia: What's in a name and its consequences?

I thought it might be helpful to explain, as simply as possible, the basis for a recent series of name changes, since some authors may be confused about these toxic and non-toxic diatom species. At the risk of over-simplification, here goes.

In terms of number of species, *Nitzschia* is one of the largest genera of the elongate, boat-shaped pennate diatoms. It has numerous delicate ridges that run across the wall, with rows of pores between them. A tubular canal runs down one edge, and a thin slot is cut along it. To hold it together there are cross bridges that create the illusion of a string of beads, under the light microscope. Species are identified (in part) by the number of these ridges and bridges. The vast majority of species are single and benthic, i.e. they live on surfaces.

However, there are some '*Nitzschia*' that look like the above description but the cells are planktonic, more sharply pointed, and occur in chains caused by the fusion of their overlapping ends. At the turn of the century, the French Peragallo brothers thought that they

were sufficiently different to warrant their own distinct genus, *Pseudonitzschia* - the name implied that the resemblance was misleading. Their proposal was generally looked at unfavourably, since the basic structure of the walls turned out to be very similar between the two, and, with a notable exception, future planktonic species were assigned to *Nitzschia*. The exception was the action of J. Frenguelli, who named a locally common species from Argentine waters as *Pseudonitzschia australis* in 1939.

In 1988, Grethe Hasle produced a very useful revision of these planktonic species which she referred to as the '*Pseudonitzschia* group' within *Nitzschia*. What to do with Frenguelli's species? Well, the usual procedure in such circumstances is to transfer it to *Nitzschia*, keeping his species name, i.e. *Nitzschia australis*. However, there already was a (different) species with that name among the hundreds of named *Nitzschia* spp. In such circumstances, a new species name is created, and Hasle chose *N. pseudoseriata* as Frenguelli's species was so much like *N. seriata*.

The discovery of DA among the *Pseudonitzschia* group (three species so far but likely to be more if past history is any indication) renewed interest in these common planktonic species. This has led to the view that they really are sufficiently distinct to warrant their own genus. Consequently, Hasle revived the Peragallos' genus, and the *Nitzschia* spp. of this group were named as *Pseudonitzschia* spp., keeping the species names wherever possible. Thus, for example, *N. pungens* became *P. pungens*, this action being referred to as a new combination. Another example is *Nitzschia pseudodelicatissima*, which is now rather bizarrely referred to as *Pseudonitzschia pseudodelicatissima*, an apparent excess of pseudosity! Note that, according to the rules of nomenclature (which are published and periodically revised), the species which Hasle had renamed, *N. pseudoseriata* had to get its first name back. It is the same organism as *Pseudonitzschia australis* - they are synonyms with the latter now being the name of choice.

This may seem confusing, but it is generally understandable, I hope.

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Laboratory studies of domoic acid production by *Pseudonitzschia pungens*

To better understand the mechanisms determining bloom dynamics and speciation of *Pseudonitzschia* (previously *Nitzschia*) *pungens* in Prince Edward Island in eastern Canada (see also article by J.C. Smith, p. 1), parallel ecophysiological and cellular studies are underway in the laboratory. Field studies and monitoring programs in Atlantic Canada have been complicated by the fact that dense blooms of *P. pungens* can be present without evidence of DA production. In the Gulf of St. Lawrence, *P. pungens* appears as two morphotypes - forma *multiseriata* (a DA producer), and forma *pungens*, a non-toxic organism. These forma are virtually indistinguishable by light microscopy. Scanning electron microscopy is used to resolve subtle differences in frustule morphology. Recently, an immunofluorescence assay has been developed that employs separate polyclonal antibodies that are

specific to cell-surface antigens of alternative forma of *P. pungens*. No cross reactions were found between the two forma, nor with about 40 other species examined. However, very slight immunolabelling was found with *P. pseudodelicatissima* and *P. australis*, two other reputed DA producers. Work at the Institute for Marine Biosciences, NRC, Halifax, on distinguishing toxic vs non-toxic species has involved molecular biology techniques, including analysis of 18S ribosomal RNA gene sequences.

Phycotoxin research relies heavily on the availability of the appropriate cultures of toxin-producing organisms. The availability of toxigenic cultures has allowed development of chemical analytical techniques, including high performance liquid chromatography (HPLC) coupled with detection by fluorescence (FD) or UV diode-array detection

(DAD), and ion-spray mass spectrometry (ISP-MS), for the analysis of DA. The manipulation of unialgal cultures in the laboratory has permitted the identification of factors influencing the growth and DA production of *P. pungens*. This work has shown that DA is not usually produced while the cells are dividing mitotically, but rather begins near the onset of the stationary phase, e.g. due to silicate (Si) limitation. Nitrogen (N) has also been found to be essential for toxin production - this is not surprising since DA is an N-containing amino acid. Other studies have shown that light is required for toxin biosynthesis and that *P. pungens* may be adapted to the low irradiance environment in which it blooms in the autumn. However, it appears that *P. pungens* has no unique adaptations for growth or toxin production at low ambient temperatures characteristic of au-

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tumn bloom conditions. Recently, *P. pungens* was grown in chemostat culture at the Department of Fisheries and Oceans (Moncton, New Brunswick). In contrast to batch cultures, *P. pungens* produced DA during active cell division phases in Si- or P-limited chemostat cultures. It may be that the pathway for DA production is turned on under nutrient-stress conditions, rather than as a response to the cessation of cellular division.

The role of bacteria in DA production is under intense investigation. It has been established that cultures rendered bacteria-free using antibiotics still produce DA, but often at substantially lower levels than untreated xenic cultures. Re-addition of bacteria has been shown to enhance DA production, and this subject is an area of continuing research. Studies are also underway to determine if bacteria from *P. pungens* cultures can produce DA in isolation. Attempts to characterize bacteria associated with *P. pungens* cultures are also in progress at the Institute for Marine Biosciences, NRC, Halifax, and at the Charleston Laboratory, National Marine Fisheries Service, South Carolina. Finally, the availability of axenic clones of *P. pungens* has facilitated study of the *in vivo* DA biosynthetic pathway.

The first DA-producing diatom, *P. pungens*, was isolated into culture soon after the original ASP incident in late autumn of 1987. However, interclonal variation in morphological and physiological characteristics is also an important issue in phytoplankton research. The Southern Gulf of St. Lawrence Culture Collection of Harmful Marine Phytoplankton was established at the Department of Fisheries and Oceans, Moncton, New Brunswick, as a species bank. This collection now contains about 60 clones each of *Pseudonitzschia pungens* f. *multiseriis* and f. *pungens*, as well as about 30 clones of *P. delicatissima*, and various isolates of other diatoms and dinoflagellates from various locations in eastern Canada.

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In the Bay of Fundy, eastern Canada

Bay of Fundy locations where domoic acid levels in shellfish have exceeded the acceptable regulatory limit for human consumption (20 µg/g).

In late July 1988, low levels of DA were detected in soft-shell clams (*Mya arenaria*) and blue mussels (*Mytilus edulis*) from the southwestern Bay of Fundy in eastern Canada. This early detection was a result of an extensive shellfish and phytoplankton monitoring program that was initiated in Canadian coastal regions following seafood poisonings (ASP) caused by the consumption of toxic mussels from eastern Prince Edward Island in late fall of 1987. The purpose of the study was to determine the geographic distribution of shellfish containing DA and to identify the organism(s) producing the toxin.

Closures of shellfish areas to harvesting due to high PSP toxin levels are not uncommon in the Bay of Fundy. However, prior to 1988, no shellfish toxicity had been associated with diatom blooms in this region. During 1988, after the implementation of the ASP monitoring program, DA was found only in shellfish collection areas in Passamaquoddy Bay (see figure). Although DA in shellfish was first detected in late July, shellfish harvesting areas remained open until 29 August, when levels of DA exceeded the Canadian regulatory limit (> 20 µg/g). Areas with unacceptable levels included: Chamcook Harbour (1), McCann's Cove (2), Magaguadavic Basin (3), Pottery Creek (4), Bocabec Cove (5) and Northern Harbour (6) (see figure). The highest levels of DA recorded in blue mussels were 74 µg/g measured at Chamcook Harbour (1) on 22 September, whereas maximum levels in soft-shell clams (53 µg/g) occurred on 29 September at

nearby McCann's Cove (2).

Analysis of phytoplankton from the Passamaquoddy Bay region showed that the pennate diatom, *Pseudonitzschia pseudodelicatissima* (formerly *Nitzschia pseudodelicatissima*), was the dominant planktonic organism when DA was detected. Plankton were collected with a 20-µm net and analyzed for DA by HPLC. The highest cell concentrations (1.20×10^6 cells/L) were found at Chamcook Harbour (1) on 23 September 1988. Several phytoplankton species from net tows containing DA were cultured; however, only *P. pseudodelicatissima* cultures produced this toxic metabolite. The cellular concentration of DA ranged from 7.0×10^{-3} to 9.8×10^{-2} µg/cell.

Both shellfish and phytoplankton samples from the Bay of Fundy have been analyzed for DA since 1988, but this toxin has not been detected in shellfish in subsequent years. Only very low levels have been measured from plankton samples collected from 1989 to 1992. Phytoplankton monitoring since 1987 indicated that 1988 was the only year that *P. pseudodelicatissima* dominated the phytoplankton for a two-month period, reaching concentrations in excess of 1.0×10^6 cells/L. Historical phytoplankton records from the Fundy region noted *P. pseudodelicatissima* in 1931, and this species has been observed annually since 1976 – it is evidently not a recent introduction to the area.

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(Cont'd from p. 1, 'Prince Edward Isl.')

The events of 1989 were very different, in that there was no significant fall diatom bloom and *P. pungens* cell densities in the Cardigan River estuary reached only 0.6×10^6 cells/L. The dry summer of previous years did not occur, nor was there any runoff increase in the fall. The two *P. pungens* morphotypes followed in secession; an early non-toxic bloom was followed by a toxic event in November.

In contrast, in 1990 a bloom of the non-toxic form occurred in October, but no toxic bloom followed. After the non-toxic bloom, the meteorological conditions were dominated by a series of violent, primarily northerly storms and the seaward dispersal of one incipient *P. pungens* bloom was documented at this time.

In 1991, an October bloom of the non-toxic form was observed again, and was followed by violent storms. A short period of calm weather in early November produced a diatom bloom (mainly *Chaetoceros* spp.), yet *P. pungens* f. *multiseries* was found in very small numbers in the Cardigan River system. In 1992, only a few *P. pungens* cells were found in this area and DA levels were barely detectable in phytoplankton samples.

We do not know why *P. pungens* f. *multiseries* has virtually disappeared from the Cardigan River region. One possibility is that the population was blown out to sea in 1990 before it had time to reproduce. Another possibility is that the species has been depleted by predators or parasites; we have recently observed that all bloom-forming *Pseudonitzschia* spp. in the region are subject to parasitism by a chytrid fungus, often at high rates of infection.

Large interannual variability is the most obvious characteristic of the late autumn blooms of *P. pungens* in PEI. One consistent feature, however, is that certain shallow estuaries of PEI have a propensity to produce late autumn diatom blooms, and that these estuaries are sufficiently well mixed, turbulent, and nutrient-rich at this time to sustain such blooms. If species successional processes operate such that *P. pungens* f.

multiseries dominates the phytoplankton during the conjunction of such favourable conditions, then a toxigenic bloom can result.

Phytoplankton monitoring programs have proven effective in detecting DA events, even at unexpected locations and times. An example of this was in New London Bay (PEI) in 1991, where the pattern observed in 1988 and 1989, i.e. a large non-toxic bloom of *P. pungens* f. *pungens* in September, followed by a much smaller toxic bloom of f. *multiseries* in November, was not repeated in 1991. Instead, a large toxic bloom of f. *multiseries* occurred in early October, and was not preceded by the non-toxic form. This situation was detected by the monitoring program in place.

For monitoring, the critical variable is the concentration of particulate DA (that within cells) in the water column. This is best determined by chemical methods, which also have the advantage of detecting DA in unknown sources – *P. pungens* is not the only known producer of DA. In summary, phytoplankton monitoring has proven to be an effective and highly economical strategy in detecting DA events in eastern PEI, particularly when coupled with chemical analyses of phytoplankton and shellfish samples.

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(1) Wright, J.L.C. et al. (1989). *Can. J. Chem.*, 67: 481.

(2) Bates, S.S. et al. (1990). *Can. J. Fish. Aqua. Sci.*, 48: 136.

(3) Addison, R.F. and J.E. Stewart. (1989). *Aquaculture*, 77: 263.

(4) Todd, E.C.D. (1993). *J. Food Protection*, 56: 69.

Future events

OCTOBER 93

Sixth International Conference on Toxic Marine Phytoplankton, 18-22 October, Nantes, France. Contact: Cité des Congrès, 5 rue Valmy, 44041 Nantes Cedex 10, France; tel: (33) 4037 4130; fax: (33) 4037 4073.

Eleventh International Symposium of the World Association of Veterinary Food Hygienists (XI WAVFH), 24-29 October, Bangkok, Thailand. Contact: Dr. Vanda Sujarit, Faculty of Veterinary Medicine, Kasetsart University, Bangkok, Bangkok 10903, Thailand; tel: (66-2) 5797539; fax: (66-2) 5798781/5790524; telex: 21957 RECOFTC TH.

The IOC-FAO Intergovernmental Panel on Harmful Algal Blooms, 2nd session, 14-16 October, Paris, France. Contact: IOC Secretariat, Paris (see address below).

NOVEMBER 93

Environmental Management of Enclosed Coastal Seas (EMECS) - Change of dates from 19-21 July to **10-13 November**, Baltimore, Maryland, USA. Contact: Helene Tenner, EMECS Secretariat, Tawes State Office Building, Taylor Avenue, Annapolis, Maryland 21401, USA; tel: (1-410) 974 5047; or Dorothy Peterson, Sea Grant College, University of Maryland, USA; fax: (1-301) 314 9581.

12th Biennial International Estuarine Research Conference, 14-18 November, Hilton Head, SC, USA. A session will focus on all aspects of phytoplankton blooms. Individuals wishing to present papers or posters should send their abstract and fee of US \$20 (made out to ERF'93 Conference) to: Kevin Sellner, Benedict Estuarine Research Laboratory, ANS, Benedict, MD 20612, USA; tel: (1-301) 274 3134; fax: (1-301) 274 3137; omnet: benedict.lab.

EDITOR'S NOTE

As indicated on p. 1, this issue of HAN has been dedicated to the problem of domoic acid in North America, especially in Canada. Our guest editor, Allan Gembella, is a member of the editorial team of scientists which was recently established to cover the various scientific fields and geographical areas with regards to harmful algae.

We had intended to publish in this issue the names and addresses of the members of this team. However, due to lack of space, this information will be included in the next issue (no. 7).

HARMFUL ALGAE NEWS

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